

PROMOTING TRADITIONAL HEALTH CARE AMONG ITINERANT WELLNESS THERAPISTS

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ABSTRACT

Hinged upon Travis' illness-wellness continuum, this study is premised on the acceptance of complementary and alternative medicine (CAM) in the broad spectrum of wellness, which is now being endorsed by health sectors, both public and private. Hospitals and wellness business centers now abound because of the therapeutic advantages brought about the non-western modalities of healing. Massage, in particular, has been a sought-after source of relief both from ailments and stress-related physical complaints. Amidst the mushrooming of clinics and wellness salons, there exists a notable niche for itinerant wellness providers. This research intended to profile the informant-itinerant wellness providers as to their experiences in CAM; identify their marketing strategies, if any; and surface circumstances of their staying power. Using the qualitative-descriptive mode of research, interviews were conducted among 10 purposively selected key informants with a mean age of 58 years old, with 23 years of experience in the industry. Clients resort to them due to exhaustion from medical interventions, for relaxation, and belief in their healing powers. Service outcome, healing touch, locus of service, age, longevity in the industry, and therapist-patient familiarity are the main reasons for their staying power.

Keywords: *Complementary and alternative medicine, hilot & massage marketing*

INTRODUCTION

Article II, Section 15 of the 1987 Philippine Constitution provides that the State shall promote the right to health of the people and instill health consciousness among them. Article XIII, Section 3 states further that the State shall afford full protection of labor, local and overseas, organized and unorganized, and promote full employment and equality of employment opportunities for all (officialgazette.gov.ph).

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), 60% of the world's population depends on traditional medicine and 80% of the population in developing countries depend almost entirely on traditional medicine practices and herbal medicines for their primary health care needs (Chikezie and Ojiako, 2015). It is the same organization (WHO) that defined wellness to be the "state of complete physical, mental, and social well-being, and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity" (who.org).

Republic Act 8423, also known as "An Act Creating the Philippine Institute of Traditional and Alternative Health Care (PITAHC) to Accelerate the Development of Traditional and Alternative Health Care in the Philippines, Providing a Traditional and Alternative Health Care Development Fund and for Other Purposes," was approved on December 7, 1997. Since then, PITAHC, which is under the aegis of the Department of Health (DOH), has been working on its mandate "to improve the quality and delivery of health care services to the Filipino people through the development of traditional and alternative health care... (pitahc.gov.ph).

The agency, located in Quezon City, has the following functions relevant in this discussion: (a) to promote and advocate the use of traditional, alternative, preventive, and curative health care modalities that have been proven safe, effective, cost effective and consistent with government standards on medical practice; (b) to develop and coordinate skills training courses for various forms of traditional and alternative health care modalities; and (c) to formulate policies to strengthen the role of traditional and alternative health care delivery system.

Complementary and alternative medicine (CAM), which falls under the points of interest of PITAHC, has various facets: traditional alternative medicine (acupuncture, ayurveda, homeopathy, naturopathy, Chinese or oriental medicine), body (chiropractic and osteopathic medicine, massage, body movement therapies, Tai-chi, Yoga), diet and herbs (dietary supplements, herbal medicine, nutrition/diet), external energy (electromagnetic therapy, Reiki, Qigong), mind (meditation, biofeedback, hypnosis), senses (art, dance, and music, visualization and guided imagery) (hopkinsmedicine.org). Among these modalities, it is massage therapy that is now starting to be popular and acceptable popularity as part of the CAM therapy movement (psycnet.apa.org). In a study to determine the knowledge, patterns of use, and attitude towards the use of CAM by herbalists and lay people, leaf extract (decoction) and traditional massage (hilot, or massage in Filipino) were

the most prevalent types of CAM across all studied areas; where widespread use was primarily because of recommendations from family members and doctors (Ching, Flores, and Acelajado, 2016). Organic word of mouth marketing is their only way of being known to their clients, and they still feel relevant because of

It now appears that, in the midst of scientific and technological breakthroughs, CAM has found a place in the wellness continuum of Travis (1972) who posited that the presence or absence of disease to demonstrate wellness was insufficient.

In his illustration (supra), the right side reflects degrees of wellness, while the left indicates degrees of illness. This paradigm has been used to describe how, even absent physical illness, one can complain of depression, anxiety or other conditions. Travis forwards that medicine typically addresses injuries, disabilities, and symptoms, to bring the individual to a "neutral point" or midway where there is no illness. However, the model demands adjusting the state of wellbeing further along the continuum towards ideal emotional and mental states. This construct presupposes that wellbeing is dynamic rather than static (Ferguson, 2013).

The Wellness Continuum is appreciated to advocate preventive treatment, which improves wellbeing before a person would present signs or symptoms of illness to protect against pathology and premature death (Thompson, 2007).

As early as 2001, Vickers & Reinish have cited Ling, who wrote that strong massage could improve the circulation of the blood and lymph. In the past 20 to 30 years, CAM therapists have adapted Swedish massage to focus on the psychological and spiritual aspects of treatment. Advantages of massage are now termed more using words such as "calmness" or "wholeness" than in terms of loosening stiff joints or improving blood flow. In contrast to the vigorous and standardized treatment recommended by Ling, current massage techniques are gentler, calming, flowing, and intuitive.

The American Massage Therapy Association (in prnewswire.com) claims that since stress, anxiety, and pain can radically limit one's lifestyle and negatively affect overall health, there are enough indications in research that prove the benefits of massage therapy as part of an approach to relieve one from stress, anxiety, and pain.

For more than 20 years, studies have shown some of the positive effects of massage therapy for relaxation. In a study on the effect of trigger point therapy (Delaney, Leong, Watkins, & Brodie, 2002), there was a significant decrease in heart rate, systolic blood pressure, and diastolic blood pressure. Measures of oxygen consumption, blood pressure, and salivary cortisol levels were all lower after a 10 to 15-minute chair massage in controlled studies (Boone, Tanner, & Radosevich in 2001; Cady & Jones in 1997; and Field, Ironson, Scafidi, Nawrocki, T., Goncalves, Burman, Pickens, Fox, Schanberg, & Kuhn in 1996). Changes in psychological states have been measured by physiological responses the Perceived Stress Scale, the POMS Depression Scale, and the Anxiety State Scale.

Research documents the effect for relief of anxiety and depression for people in a wide range of health situations (Jane, Wilkie, Gallucci, Beaton, Huang, 2009; Imanishi, Kuriyama, Shigemori, Watanabe, Aihara, Kita, Sawai, Nakajima, Yoshida, Kunisawa, Kawase, and Fukui in 2007; Smith, Reeder, Daniel, Baramée, Hagman in 2003; and Hughes, Ladas, Rooney, and Kelly in 2008).

In an annual consumer survey conducted by The American Massage Therapy Association in 2017, when one complains of muscle strain and soreness leading to serious or chronic pain, massage therapy is showing positive results. Consumers are learning its value, as 41% of American adults who availed of massage in the past 5 years indicate they sought it for pain relief. Moreover, a meta-analysis of research on massage therapy for pain conducted by Samueli Institute in 2016 concluded that

massage therapy should be strongly recommended for pain management. The analysis reviewed 67 published studies on the impact of massage therapy on pain (Crawford, Boyd, Paat, et al, 2016).

In the Philippines, traditional healing is a part of the Filipino culture or generational heritage or legacy, and is still being practiced; especially in the rural areas (Rebuya & Lasarte & Amador, 2020). Traditional healers have been a part of the Philippine Health Care Delivery System (Galan, 2018).

A study aimed to document traditional healing practices in Zamboanga City found that traditional healers are sought by people across all economic standings. The most sought-after practice is hilot (subada) where the healer conducts massage upon the affected body area using coconut oil or commercial ointment (Molina, Esperat, and Gracia, 2020).

In a research conducted to determine the knowledge, patterns of use, and attitude towards the use of complementary and alternative medicines (CAM) by herbalists and lay people from selected areas in the upland portion of the province of Cavite, it was found out that of nine (9) forms of CAM documented as used by the interviewees, leaf extract (decoction) and traditional massage (hilot) were the most prevalent types; with their widespread use mainly because of recommendations from family members and medical doctors. Among the various ailments that CAM intended to heal were: common colds, cough, and fever. The study observed a generally positive attitude towards the use of all forms of CAM, and concluded that CAM plays a major health care role among the interviewees (Ching, Flores, and Acelajado (2016).

Given that Filipinos, especially rural folks, have the propensity to avail of traditional healing in lieu of modern/scientific/western medicine, it comes not as a surprise that even Filipinos based abroad, in this case, the United States, accept medical pluralism which is understood as the combination of conventional healing and CAM. Not a big number of US-based Filipino adults use CAM to treat pain-related and cardiovascular conditions, with recommendations coming from family and friends. Most common reasons for using CAM for treatment of health condition were: CAM is natural, with a holistic approach, and could be taken/practiced independently. (Reynaldon & Choi, 2018)

In a chapter on CAM in his book *Health Law and Medical Ethics in Singapore*, Yew (2020) asserts the complementarity between CAM and conventional medicine, if only to alleviate stress, reduce pain and anxiety, and manage symptoms. CAM is resorted to in place of western medicine, and is typically built upon homeopathic and naturopathic medicine. Integrative medicine, which combines complementary therapies with mainstream patient care, has been gaining popularity among patients with cancer and other chronic illness. Certain hospitals in Singapore integrate acupuncture services into their provision of medical services. The traditional Chinese medicine (TCM) practitioner should ensure that the patient has consented to the treatment or procedure. Proper explanation of at least the broad nature and purpose of the treatment or procedure should be given by the TCM practitioner in order to avoid allegations under the tort of battery. The “rules and standards of the TCM profession” determine whether any conduct complained of amounts to professional misconduct.

In the province of Nueva Vizcaya, there are two (2) government hospitals offering the wellness model through CAM: The Region II Trauma and Medical Center (R2TMC) and the Lt. Tidang Memorial Hospital (LTMH).

With a 500-bed capacity, the R2TMC is located in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, offering the following services: internal medicine, family and community medicine, pediatrics, obstetrics and gynecology, orthopedics, ophthalmology, ears, nose, throat (ENT), head and neck, surgery, neurology, dermatology, dental medicine, endoscopy, psychiatric and behavioral health clinic, violence against women and children (VAWC) desk, HIV and AIDS core team (HACT), tb-dots, rehabilitation medicine, pulmonary function test, animal bite treatment center, and complementary and alternative health care clinic (CAHC). on a 24-hour function are the following departments: pharmacy, laboratory, radiology, and central supply and sterile unit. the R2TMC is under the DOH (riitmc.doh.gov.ph).

On the other hand, the LTMH has a 20-bed capacity, and is located in Kayapa, Nueva Vizcaya, and is under the jurisdiction of the Provincial Government of Nueva Vizcaya. The official website of the province reveals that the hospital offers the following services: in-patient/out-patient care, emergency room services, OR/DR/RR services, new-born screening and RH/FP itinerary, laboratory, radiology, dental, pharmacy, and dietary services, alternative health care services (acupuncture and acupressure, ventosa, ear detoxification), and ambulance services (uhmis2.doh.gov.ph and nuevavizcaya.gov.ph).

Given that these two (2) hospitals are within the relative reach of the populace, the researchers still note that there are patients who approach individuals known to offer CAM services outside the ambit of these government health facilities.

A search on the theme: “massage nueva vizcaya” using the google search engine on the world wide web would reveal at least ten (10) establishments with any of the following terms attached to their business name: spa, beauty and wellness, facial and spa center, nail bar and body

spa, health; indicating that wellness is not just the domain of hospitals and similar medical facilities. This further points out that wellness may be sought even without any medical referral.

Field (2016) conducted a massage therapy research review which revealed massage therapy to have beneficial effects on conditions such as prenatal depression, preterm infants, full-term infants, autism, skin conditions, pain syndromes including arthritis and fibromyalgia, hypertension, autoimmune conditions including asthma and multiple sclerosis, immune conditions including HIV and breast cancer and aging problems including Parkinson's and dementia. While many of the studies have involved comparisons between massage therapy and standard treatment control groups, several have compared different forms of massage (swedish versus thai massage), and different active therapies such as massage versus exercise. Typically, the massage therapy groups have shown more positive effects than the control or comparison groups. This may be because massage therapy provides more stimulation of pressure receptors. Some of the researchers have assessed physical, physiological and biochemical effects, although most have relied exclusively on self-report measures. Despite these methodological problems and the dearth of research from the U.S., the massage therapy profession has grown significantly and massage therapy is increasingly practiced in traditional medical settings, highlighting the need for more rigorous research.

While it is admitted that alternative healing has a place in the world of conventional (western) medicine, one would wonder how CAM can be sold so convincingly to people so as to afford them a non-hospital avenue towards wellness, one that is devoid of the equipment and facilities of both pharmacy-sourced pills and machine-generated apparatus, including a roster of staff trained in the art and science of CAM.

Thus, in the context of this study, the following terms are operationally defined, unless otherwise stated: (a) *Traditional Health Care or Alternative Health Care* refers to the non-conventional therapeutic or preventive practices that are not included in the areas or subjects in the Physicians' Licensure Examination as administered by the Professional Regulations Commission. These subjects are: (1) Biochemistry, (2) Anatomy and Histology, (3) Microbiology and Parasitology, (4) Physiology, (5) Legal Medicine, Ethics, and Medical Jurisprudence. (6) Pathology, (7) Pharmacology and Therapeutics, (8) Surgery and Ophthalmology, Otolaryngology, and Rhinology, (9) Medicine, (10) Obstetrics and Gynecology, (11) Pediatrics and Nutrition, and (12) Preventive Medicine and Public Health (prc.gov.ph); (b) *Marketing Strategy* is the art and science employed by the informants so the public they may be aware of and patronize the services they offer; and (c) *Itinerant Wellness Therapists* are those who offer CAM to clients outside of the facilities of established medical facilities. They may conduct their sessions in their own homes or in the homes of their clients, but not in the clinics or hospitals.

Given the foregoing theoretical and empirical groundedness of this study, it is then the intention of this research to: (1) profile the informant-itinerant wellness therapists as to their experiences in CAM; (2) identify their marketing strategies, if any; and (3) surface circumstances of their staying power.

METHODOLOGY

This qualitative study was conducted in the province of Nueva Vizcaya, particularly in the municipalities of Bagabag, Bayombong, Solano, and Villaverde; which are located near known medical facilities such as the R2TMC, Salubris Medical Center, PLT Hospital, Nueva Vizcaya Medical Mission Group Hospital Inc. (MMG Hospital), and other private clinics and medical centers. Through the purposive sampling using the snowball technique, it was able to identify ten (10) informants who are involved in the different components of CAM. Interview sessions were scheduled, and the researchers sought them in their respective homes.

Document-scanning, ocular inspection and key informant interviews served as the main sources of data in this study. Documents included a review of the CAM services offered by the hospitals and the wellness treatments available in commercial spas.

The researchers formulated a questionnaire that would best embody the objectives of this study. The whole months of January and February 2021 were dedicated to identifying and establishing connections with the key informants so as to be able to set an interview time at a date and venue convenient to both key informant and researchers. The informants were oriented as to the rationale of the study being conducted, and they willingly acquiesced to be a participant therein. The questions were prepared in English, but the researchers are well-versed in Filipino and Ilocano, thereby facilitating the question and answer phase of the data-gathering portion of the study. Consent was sought from the informants, and they willingly gave a code name in the event that these may possibly be used in the discussion of this research. Throughout all the interviews, the researchers took note of the answers and wrote them down in the matrix provided them as guide. Follow-up questions were raised as the need arose. The interviews were then transcribed in tabular form to surface the most recurrent themes for analysis and interpretation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Section 1. Profile of Key Informants

Analysis of the data collected was conducted first by identifying common replies or themes among the informants, and designating colors for them. In this way, it was easier for the researchers to classify both points of convergence and divergence among the answers of the therapists.

Describing the informants offered a clearer picture of the circumstances surrounding each of them. Code names or pseudonyms were provided each individual to maintain confidentiality of person.

Ben is a forty (40)-year-old totally blind male resident of Sta. Rosa, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, who has been into massage therapy for twenty-one (21) years now. Sessions are held either in a private room in his home, or in the residence or office of the client. He learned how to be a therapist through a training that the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD) offers persons with disabilities (PWD) like him. Ben offers combination shiatsu, swedish and reflexology massages to his clients who are mostly male. According to him, clients resort to CAM principally because “*mauma dan toi katotomar ti agas*,” (they have already reached their saturation point drinking medicines), or for treatment of strokes, or simply for relaxation.

Berta is married to Ben. She is 50 years old, and is has partial is also a recipient of the DSWD training for PWDs where she and Ben met. Just like Ben, she had been in the wellness industry for the past twenty-one (21) years now. She caters only to female clients who either go to their house, or whom she treats either in their home or office. Clients go to her for relaxation of muscles or to reduce stress.

Neneng is from Bintawan Norte, Villaverde, Nueva Vizcaya. At sixty-six (66) years old, she has been servicing clients for thirty (30) years now. Her male and female clientele include residents of nearby towns Solano, Bayombong, Aritao, and neighboring province of Ifugao. Whenever she goes to Canada where her daughter is based, or in the US, she also treats Filipinos to massage of hilot (traditional Filipino massage) who wish to seek relief from muscle pains and treatment for strokes.

Nes is fifty-one (51) years old, and a resident of St. Rosa, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, where she conducts her therapy sessions. She goes as far as Mountain Province to relieve male and female clients from their muscle pains through sessions of reflexologym, swedish, shiatsu, tuina, or thai massage. She trained under a private training center, and has been treating clients for more than two (2) years now.

Ben is a seventy-nine (79) resident of La Torre, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, but who goes as far as Europe (Austria, Germany, Switzerland) or as near as Quezon Province, Isabela, Cavite or as close as Solano, Aritao Dupax del Norte in Nueva Vizcaya to continue his massage service which has been going on for the past thirty (30) years now. He was trained in Mindanao in a training center managed by Japanese where he learned clinical reflexology, although he includes hilot in his service menu as well. People go to Ben because they are not contented with the treatments of licensed physical therapists who are more into the use of equipment, and the clients prefer hands-on therapy treatment.

Aldrin is forty (40) years old, and a resident of San Pedro, Bagabag, Nueva Vizcaya. He has been offering massage services for the past ten (10) years now. While his home is open for sessions, some clients prefer to be treated in their respective homes. He did not undergo any formal training, he just discovered his interest in massage therapy, and it was his grandfather (also a wellness therapist) who handed him the knowledge and skills of wellness therapy. He treats clients in emergency situations, and there are some who were confined in the hospital, and were not cured.

Edgar is from San Pedro, Bagabag, Nueva Vizcaya. At seventy-two (72) years old, he has been into massage therapy for the past thirty-one (31) years now. He mainly treats clients at his home. He claims to have inherited his massage skills from his “apong lakay” (male ascendant) whom he watched treat clients earlier on. He offers “hilot” and ventosa, especially for animal bites. His clients came to know of his skill in healing, that is why they resort to his services.

Berong is a sixty-seven (67) year-old male from Careb, Bagabag, Nueva Vizcaya, who boasts of thirty-six (36) years of wellness experience which he conducts either at his home or at his clients'. Though he did not undergo any training of the wellness regime, he claims to have learned of the skills in massage therapy through divine intervention as he sought help from an “espiritista” who was based abroad. Clients approach him because they are not able to afford hospital bills.

Glo is from Aggub, Solano, Nueva Vizcaya. At fifty-eight (58) years old, she has been to various countries treating patients in Israel, Japan, and Hong Kong. She was trained in Tibet where she learned how to increase her healing power, and she is guided by a book on healing. Just like Berong, she attributes her knowledge and skills in wellness therapy through an epiphany (apparition of God). She offers “hilot” and ventosa to her patients who consulted doctors who cleared them of any ailment. Despite such clearance/s, they still had complaints of physical pain; hence, they resort to Glo's faith healing.

Aurea is a sixty (60) year-old from Lactawan, Solano, Nueva Vizcaya. In her twenty (20) years of treating clients at her home or in their residence in cases of emergency, she does not claim to have undergone any sort of training at all, because she only offers spiritual healing. Equating “hilot” to healing touch, Aurea shared that she had some clients brought to her house by ambulance coming straight from the hospital.

In sum, there were ten (10) key informants in this study: five (5) males and five (5) females), their average age being fifty-eight (58) years old, most of whom have undergone some kind of training either by an agency or by an elder; their average years of being in the itinerant wellness industry being twenty-three (23) years. Most of them conduct their services in their respective homes or in the residences or offices of their clients. Reasons why clients resort to wellness therapy include: exhaustion from medical interventions, for relaxation or to reduce stress, and belief in the power of healing from the therapist.

The Bureau of Local Employment (BLE) under the jurisdiction of the Department of Labor and Employment (DOLE) enumerates the following basic educational requirement for one to be a qualified massage therapist: “At least a high school graduate with appropriate training from local or international training institutions and/or associations duly recognized by the proper authorities is the requirement to be a Massage Therapist. Licensure from the Department of Health is also required to practice massage therapy. To qualify for licensure, the person must meet the following basic requirements: (1) at least 18 years of age or has received a high school diploma or graduate equivalency diploma; (2) has completed a course of study at a recognized massage school or has completed an apprenticeship program that meets standards approved by the Board of Massage Therapy; and (3) has received a passing grade on an examination administered by the Department of Health” (ble.dole.gov.ph).

Despite their lack of the requirements as identified, still, the informants are sought by clients, who are of more or less equal distribution by sex, and whose majority belong to the age range of forty (40) to sixty-five (65) years old. In the United States, the average age of massage therapists working in spas and nail salons is forty-two (42) years old (www.datausa.io).

Section 2. Marketing Strategies

This portion intended to identify the marketing strategies, if any, of the key informants vis-à-vis those of brick and mortar spa clinics within the locality.

Marketing Strategy is the art and science employed by the informants so the public may be aware of and patronize the services they offer. It is the way that customers are enticed by (service) providers, in this case itinerant massage therapists, so that clients will get to know them, will patronize the services they offer, return to the same therapist for a repeat of the service rendered because of client-satisfaction, let others know of the business.

The Online Marketing Institute (OMI) in onlinemarketinginstitute.org enumerates the following traditional marketing strategies: (a) **signages** are visual attractions that inform the viewer of the name of the business and the services it offers. They are usually seen in front of the building where the business is being conducted; (b) **billboards** are more common in highways and hallways, away from the actual store or business place. This mode uses less text and more images, as it targets more on a viewer who is on the move and who is far from the billboard, hence the bigger-than-life size of the material; (c) **direct mail** is the employment of postal service where printed materials are sent to prospective clients who may be interested in the products or services being offered. It is not just easier to understand, it also has a greater power to influence readers; and (d) **flyers and brochures** are print-outs that are distributed to potential clients. These bear basic information regarding a product or service, and usually contain ways to contact the business.

In all of the visits of the researchers upon the homes of the key informants, never did they encounter any signage, billboard, flyer, or brochure within the massage area; never have the informants used social media as an advertising avenue; so much unlike the two (2) hospitals earlier discussed where the wellness services are enumerated in websites, and so much different from the commercial spas visited by the researchers which had large signages and billboards, and flyers and brochures very conspicuous in the lobbies.

Telemarketing involves outbound and inbound telephone calls that invite clients to patronize a service or a product. It also aims to assist customers in the use of commodity purchased (onlinemarketinginstitute.org). While it is true that clients get in touch with the therapists via cellphone calls (with some cellphones not personally owned by the therapists), some of the clients do not use the telephone, but instead proceed to the house of the therapist if only to set a schedule for a massage session. In this wise, the service truly becomes a brick and mortar store where there is a physical presence of a business in a building or other structure (Krishnamurthy, 2020).

Kundu, Supratim and Rajan (2017) mention another classic marketing method which is word of mouth (WOM) or consumer-to-consumer interaction, which has been the center of discourse in various research undertakings. Researchers have already shown the growing influence of WOM and

it has been recognized by the marketers to be a highly credible form of marketing information. WOM marketing is also understood as information spread from one person to another based on recommendation. Organic WOM occurs naturally when people become advocates because they are happy with a product and have a natural desire to share their support and enthusiasm. In organic WOM, the clients spontaneously share their experiences (good or bad) with a brand, and, in so sharing, influence their listeners to decide whether or not to patronize said product or service. On the other hand, amplified WOM is when marketers invite people to speak well of a certain product or service; and, in so endorsing, create a positive purchase impact upon whoever is the listener or audience targeted by the endorser or influencer (bigcommerce.com).

In the commercial towns on Bayombong and Solano abound two (2) notable spas or massage centers which offer thai body massage, thai body massage with oil, swedish massage, ventosa massage, hot oil massage, aroma therapy massage with hot pads and herbal balls, and hot stone massage. Purple Spa Aesthetic Skin Clinic (Purple Spa) is a single proprietorship located in Bayombong, while Nuat Thai Massage (Nuat Thai) is a business franchise located in Solano. Both establishments have a considerable following on social media, where Purple Spa has two thousand, eight hundred and forty-one (2,841) followers, and Nuat Thai has one thousand, eight hundred and sixty-seven. The two (2) establishments have flyers and posters displayed in conspicuous places in the locality, and their social media pages includes a menu of the services they offer.

Nuat Thai advertises the following services as appearing in its social media page: Nuat Thai Foot Massage, Thai Back Massage, Thai Head, Back, and Shoulder Massage, Thai Body Massage, Thai Body Massage with Oil, Swedish Massage, Ventosa Massage, Hot Oil Massage, Aromatherapy Massage with Hot Pads and Herbal Balls, Hot Stone Massage, among others (facebook.com/NuatThaiSolano).

In its Facebook page, Purple Spa offers the following: Hair and Scalp Massage, Swedish Massage, Shiatsu Massage, BenGay Massage, Ventosa, Royal Thai Massage, Purple Massage, Foot Spa Therapy, Hand Spa Therapy, among others in the array of services available therein (facebook.com/ThePurpleSpa).

When asked how clients came to know about the services they offer, the key informants were one in saying that they depend on word-of-mouth, where friends and satisfied clients share their favorable experiences (relief from stress, healing from ailment) to others similarly situated. When asked if they have any social media account that would count for e-marketing, all of them answered in the negative, saying that the cellphone is the only way they are contacted by their clients for bookings and appointments.

When asked, "Do you ask your clients to recommend you?" all but one (1) responded in the negative. The only one who answered that he requests for a recommendation is Fred, the totally blind therapist, probably due to the fact that this is his main source of income. From the preceding then, it can be safely gleaned that the itinerant wellness therapists interviewed totally depended on organic word-of-mouth marketing, which is the least expensive among all the traditional marketing strategies known.

Marketers find WOM advantageous since sources of this word-of-mouth advertising are mostly personal, and not subject to persuasion from the business for personal gains or subject to being biased. This has a positive effect on the advertising campaign as it reveals how consumers honestly experienced a product or service, and the motivation or curiosity to try the business increases, since the recommendation comes from a trusted reliable source (Boyer, Edmondson, Baker, Solomon, 2015).

However, WOM also has its downsides. It may sometimes not be beneficial in changing or influencing consumer's attitudes and perception especially from an organic source as negative conversations may be held about the brand (Boyer, Edmondson, Baker, Solomon, 2015), especially so when the organic source does not find the product useful and may have a negative perception of the product, which is then shared. Baker, Donthu, and Kumar (2016) maintain that although positive word-of-mouth positively influences purchase intention while negative word-of-mouth decreases customer purchase intention, the effect is not the same. Compared with positive word-of-mouth, negative word-of-mouth has a larger effect on purchase intentions because not only is a business not patronized, it is also, in a manner of speaking, spoken ill of; and, in the case of the itinerant wellness providers, unsatisfied clients with unfavorable reviews or non-recommendations might be an anathema to the business since clients complaining of physical pains or ailments who talk to similarly-situated people tend to believe the dissatisfaction of customers, and are not willing to risk their health upon a non-satisfactory massage therapy.

One more criticism about this marketing strategy is that people tend to be turned off and feel deceived when they find out that a certain influencer may have benefitted either directly or indirectly in a word-of-mouth endorsement (Boyer, Edmondson, Baker, Solomon, 2015). This may cause consumers to change their views, which can have a negative impact on the product reputation.

Purcarea (2019) speculates that healthcare is a *sui generis* in the field of marketing in that basic tenets in promoting a service or a product may not be applicable as far as advertising health care is concerned, quoting Thomas (2008) in saying that healthcare needs its own tactic in approaching and presenting certain attributes that are not present in other industries. However, despite the uniqueness of healthcare marketing since it features concepts, methods, and techniques indigenous to it, it (healthcare) is considered an interdisciplinary field since the return of investment (ROI) is not quantifiable in terms of money. This is because the effectiveness of healthcare is detected in the image of a healthy population using such variables as the detection of a chronically ill category of people, ensuring the treatment of ill people by going through the whole rehabilitation process, professional reintegration, social reintegration of ill people, among others. It is then safe to say that the promoting healthcare is demanded by the issues of health in a certain community.

The same author, Purcarea, in a 2017 study says that a successful marketing strategy comprises an exhaustive examination of the patients' needs, detecting unknown needs, and proposing new health services (or products) that patients have not expressly asked for.

The promotion of healthcare services differs from the first place through the nature of the need for health services. Secondly, the beneficiary may not be the aim of the campaign, the medic being the party who decides what, where, when, and how much will be provided for a particular service. It may be the doctor, the health plan representative, a family member who decides for the patient. Healthcare services also differ where what is offered may not be understood clearly because of medical jargon, since the procedures used, especially those technology-based, are complicated and difficult to explain to a person who is not familiar in that particular discipline.

Healthcare marketing allows healthcare professionals to create, communicate, and provide value to their target market. Modern marketers start from customers rather than from products or services. They focus more on building a long-lasting relationship, rather than in ensuring a single transaction. Their objective is to establish a high level of consumer satisfaction so that they return to the same supplier. Although consumers usually get most of a product/service information through commercial media, the most important information comes from recommendations or from publicly available independent authorities. The two categories of sources provide complementary functions; commercial media – informs, while personal or expert sources legitimize or potentiate the evaluation process. For example, doctors find out about medical innovations from commercial sources, but they refer to fellow doctors for verification or legitimate opinions.

In the case of the key informants, without having any social media portal to promote their wares, they rely greatly on word-of-mouth marketing; which veers away from the above discussion in that they (itinerant wellness therapists) are totally independent of each other, perhaps even unknown to each other, and they work without any reference nor referral to and from their peers. While it is true that some clients may have been recommended by medical doctors, or may have at least consulted medical experts, or that the therapists always inquire about the client's medical condition pre-massage service, rarely or perhaps never has it ever happened that referrals were exchanged from one *hilot* to another as a way of marketing strategy.

In the case where the doctor, the health plan representative, or a family member would decide on the treatment of a patient, it often happens that the clients themselves demand or dictate what the therapist should do, and on what area should there be more pressure. Hence, the advertising of the massage therapy service or even the treatment of a client is indeed, *sui generis*, or one of its kind.

Over the past years, healthcare has experienced many marketing styles that have essentially changed the way they are advertised. These styles or trends are as follow: from a mass marketing approach to a more specific approach; from image marketing to service marketing; from "one measure for all" to personalization; from the emphasis on a health episode to a long-lasting relationship; from "ignoring" the market, to market intelligence; and from low-tech to high-tech.

Section 3. Staying Power

Staying power is simply understood as longevity or the permanence of a business that is able to withstand the test of time and the challenges of competitors and other underlying threats thereto. What are the factors that make itinerant wellness providers stay put and stay strong despite the advent of spas, the emergence of friendlier technology, and the entrance of therapists trained using institutionalized standards?

The average length of time dedicated by the key informants into the industry is twenty-three (23) years, and there does not seem to be an end seen to the itinerant wellness business. The oldest among the informants (Ben, 79 years old), has more than thirty (30) years of experience relieving people of their pains through massage therapy. The youngest (Fred and Aldrin, both 40 years old) have been treating clients for the past twenty-one (21) and ten (10) years, respectively – way beyond the years since the establishment of Purple Spa and Nuat Thai.

Despite the air-conditioned confines of these commercial spas equipped with piped music and assured of clean sheets and towels, still, there are people who prefer the itinerant therapists over those which are of the brick and mortar type.

Why so? From the point of view of the key informants, they say that the clients feel contented and relaxed after a session, “kaadwan ket kayat da ti hard massage” (most wish hard massage), home service where the therapist goes to the house of the clients instead of the other way around, client-loyalty, expertise and years of service as a therapist, sincerity in the service, track record: “adu kanu naagasakun,” (I have already healed so many) “nalaingak kanu nga agagas (I am good in healing), healing touch.

The above responses can be summed thus: clients prefer itinerant therapists over brick and mortar spa centers for the following reasons: service outcome “adu kanu naagasakun,” (I have already healed so many) “nalaingak kanu nga agagas (I am good in healing), healing touch, “kaadwan ket kayat da ti hard massage” (most wish hard massage); locus of service (home service), age; and therapist-patient familiarity.

Service outcome is understood as the feedback from clients’ post-service. Statements such as “we are relaxed,” nagmayat rikna na,” (I feel relieved) usually emanate from the clients when the massage is done. The key informants inquire whether or not the clients feel relieved or not after the session. According to the therapists, they have more satisfied clients over un-satisfied one – or that never did they have any dissatisfied client at all; in fact, they have repeat clients not because they are not contented with the previous service rendered upon them, but because they wish to have a repeat of the sense of relief and relaxation that they have experienced in previous encounters with the same therapist.

The **healing touch** refers to the relief of clients with medical conditions. It was mentioned previously that some clients were either seen by medical doctors or have been confined in the hospital, or have been declared a clean bill of health but kept on complaining of physical unease. It is safely supposed that these clients were eased of their complaints after seeing a wellness therapist. But whether or not the ease is permanent is a delimitation of this study.

The **locus of service** also plays a role in the staying power of itinerant wellness therapists. Since the sessions are conducted either in the residence of the clients or in the house of the therapists, the homey atmosphere adds to the come-on factor. Nosocomophobia is hospital fear or an extreme phobia of getting treated by doctors, which may include surgery and medicines. People suffering from this sort of anxiety have risks of high blood pressure, especially when consulting doctor or when getting into an operation theatre. Hospital fear is categorized into many types such as fear of doctors, fear of needles, fear of surgery, fear of germs and fear of death. Fear of hospitals can be caused due to a traumatic event that has struck the person badly. In some cases, hospital fear may be caused due to Trypanophobia (Fear of needles) or even the fear of seeing blood. Some people also develop this condition due to the fear of taking medication (Roy, 2017). In the age of deliveries-at-your-doorstep and enjoying the comforts of the home, there is a seemingly inviting prospect for clients to prefer being treated in the comfort of the home – theirs or the therapist’s. This may be due to the fear of the structure that is the clinic or the hospital, which is more known to treat sickness and disease, rather than to encourage wellness. Hence, treatment at home is not being in the hospital; therefore, there is a denial of being unwell, even if as early as 1955, it was already admitted that denial of illness can be understood as an orderly and understandable adaptation pattern to stress (JAMA, 1955).

Age, in this discussion as a factor in the staying power of itinerant therapists despite massage therapies offered in accredited hospital and in wellness centers with trained employees, is two-pronged: age of the therapist and years in the industry or longevity. The average age of the key informant is fifty-eight (58) years old, with the youngest male therapist at forty (40), and the female at fifty (50). The most senior of the males is seventy-nine (79) and for the females, sixty-six (66) years old. Fifty percent (50%) or five (5) out of ten (10) of the informants are above the age of 60, which Quisumbing Torres (2017), a law firm specializing in labor laws, says is the age for optional retirement in the private sector, with sixty-five (65) being the mandatory retirement age. A simple layman’s understanding of the term “retirement” would be a stoppage from one’s position or occupation or from one’s active working life. In this sense, Neneng (60), Ben (79), Edgardo (72), Berong (67), and Aurea (60) should already be withdrawn from work, and enjoying the fruits of retirement, if any. However, these informants abovementioned, are those who are most active in the industry in that they did not seem to forward any indication that, in the proximate future, they shall stop from treating clients. Eyjólfsdóttir, Baumann, Agahi and Lennartsson (2020) citing the study of Denton and Spencer (2009) echoed the latter’s finding that there is no agreed measure and that no one measure dominates as far as concept of retirement is concerned i.e., that there was no consensus on the definition of retirement and that no standard seemed to be more frequently used than others.

Respect for elders is foremost among all the treasured values among Filipinos. Inherent among elders in the Filipino setting to enjoy a high level of esteem as they are seen to occupy a certain status of respect and privilege even among non-family members. Jocano, in 1998, described

the traditional Filipino society being “organized on the basis of generation and concept of seniority which involved deference to and respect for older persons, regardless of gender (Del Villar, 2015). Another dimension of age as a determinant of the staying power of itinerant wellness therapists is age in the industry, i.e., how many years the therapist has been immersed in such healing modality. The average years the informants are into CAM is twenty-three (23) years; with “Nes” rendering the least number of years at more than two (2) years, and Berong with the most years of experience at thirty-six (36).

Corollary to the previous statement regarding the esteem Filipinos hold towards the elderly is the respect they have for those who have been long in the industry in that they are considered the experts or bearers of the skill, the pioneers in the locality, and the learned and gifted among the others. The natural course of things would be for clients to prefer tried and tested suppliers of whatever service or product. Longevity is given premium by clients when they choose which therapist to go to. Only the best survives, as they say; leaving those relatively new in the field almost without clients. This is seen in Kennedy and Munk (2017) who concluded in a study that massage therapy is often considered as a second career and, unfortunately, many new to the field are not staying long in their new massage therapy careers.

Patient-therapist relationship refers to the connection established between both parties in the course of their sessions. The hospital environment remains to be daunting for clients, as discussed above; and it was observed by the researchers that when clients avail of massage services in spas, they are welcomed into a semi-lighted area, where silence is strongly observed, since the only sound heard is the soft piped music to enhance relaxation. Hence, the relationship between supplier and client in hospitals and spas is somewhat impersonal even if the supplier kneads the body parts of the client, which is considered as a private activity. When the itinerant wellness therapists handle their clients, there is no requirement to be silent; conversation is engaged upon. Stories are exchanged, pleasantries are encouraged, guards are suddenly put-off. When clients sometimes seek massage and spend that time talking about private matters, it is a massage therapist’s obligation to keep information shared by a client confidential. Spreading this information may not only damage the client’s reputation but does not demonstrate a reputable or ethical way engage a massage client (What is the massage therapist’s code of ethics? in beautyce.com). The confidentiality and privacy accorded the massage ritual allows both therapist and client to put their guards down and discuss matters related to family, work, or other personal issues. The therapist becomes not only a therapist, but gets transformed into a confidant.

Conclusions and Recommendations

The study concludes that the 10 key informants in this study are adults in their late 50’s. They have undergone some kind of training either through an agency or by an elder; their services span more than two decades who either provide them in their respective homes or in the residences or offices of their clients. Prime reasons why clients resort to wellness therapy include: exhaustion from medical interventions, for relaxation or to reduce stress, and belief in the power of healing from the therapist. The only marketing strategy utilized by the itinerant wellness providers is the organic word-of-mouth strategy, in that they do not have signages, billboards, flyers or brochures, websites, nor social media portals that advertise their services. They rely on the word-of-mouth recommendations of satisfied clients without prodding them (clients) to do so. Lastly, the service outcome, healing touch, locus of service, age, longevity in the industry, and therapist-patient familiarity are the main reasons for their staying power.

In the light of the findings and conclusions derived from this study, the researchers strongly recommend the use of social media as a way for prospective clients to seek the itinerant wellness therapists; this may be done through the creation of an account per therapist. Same modality may be used for the therapists to make known the services they offer. While telephone calls may suffice for some, it is as well an accepted fact that the reach of social media is farther, thereby expanding the possibility of clients to be able to look for what and whom they want within a shorter span of time. This is premised upon the possibility that the therapists themselves are oriented as to the management of social media. Another recommendation is for their services to be included in “market places” on social media where netizens would have access to their contact details. A separate and distinct social media page may be created advertising the therapists’ services. This may be called “Wellness Therapists in Nueva Vizcaya” which would be specifically for therapists to allow other people to contact them and contract their services. In the pursuit of further knowledge about this subject, it would interest future researchers to conduct replicate studies - this time involving the massage clients in order to triangulate the findings in this current study, especially on the marketing strategies and the staying power of itinerant wellness providers, as well as an exploration or documentation on the effectiveness of the healing touch to ease the pain – whether temporary or permanent.

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